

Data management

Description of data provenance and ethical considerations for all data used in [1]

Data

All data used for this project was collected retrospectively and did not include data from clinical trials. All of the data shared through GE Healthcare was collected with informed consent and deidentified in accordance with the requirements of applicable privacy, data and patient protection laws such that the data no longer identifies the patient who is the subject of the data and does not constitute personal data.

Triplane data

The triplane dataset consists of 240 recordings and utilizes subsets of several different datasets. 195 of the recordings are from datasets approved by the Regional Committees for Medical and Health Research Ethics, the institutions, and the regional Data Security Officer under the TRUST (7160 and 135346) and HUNT4 studies (2018/2416).

45 recordings were shared with GE Healthcare from three different sites in accordance with data sharing agreements described in the list below.

- TRUST (7160 and 135346)
- HUNT4 (2018/2416)
- GE Healthcare (GEHC)
 - Danderyd Hospital, Stockholm, Sweden – data sharing agreement signed 28-Mar-2018
 - University of Padua, Dept. of Cardiac, Thoracic and Vascular Sciences, Padua, Italy – data sharing agreement signed 22-Mar-2016
 - University of California – San Francisco (UCSF), San Francisco, USA – data sharing agreement signed 20-Jun-2019

External (APLAX) data

The external APLAX dataset used for validation was collected at Oslo University Hospital shared with GE Healthcare in accordance with a data sharing agreement between the two parties as members of ProCardio (funded by the Research Council of Norway, project no: 309762).

- Oslo University Hospital (OUS), Oslo, Norway – data sharing agreement signed 23-Nov-2021

References

- [1] B. S. Fermann *et al.*, “Cardiac valve event timing in echocardiography using deep learning and triplane recordings,” *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, pp. 1–10, 2024, ISSN: 2168-2194, 2168-2208. DOI: [10.1109/JBHI.2024.3373124](https://doi.org/10.1109/JBHI.2024.3373124).